

Early Detection with Explainability of Network Attacks Using Deep Learning

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Abstract—In previous work, we proposed an end-to-end early intrusion detection system to identify network attacks in real-time before they complete and could cause more damage to the system under attack. To implement the approach, we have trained a Convolution Neural Network (CNN) model with an attention mechanism in a supervised manner to extract relevant features from raw network traffic in order to classify network flows into different types of attacks. In this preliminary work, we discuss and compare the results of using the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) model with an attention mechanism to detect the attacks earlier. Furthermore, the model not only classifies the given flow but also ranks the packets in the flow with respect to their importance for prediction. This ranking can be used for further investigation of the detected network attacks. We empirically evaluate our approach on the CICIDS2017 dataset. Preliminary results show that the RNN model with an attention mechanism can achieve better classification performance than our previous work with the CNN model.

Index Terms—Early IDS, Attention Mechanism, Deep learning, Recurrent Neural Network, GRU

I. INTRODUCTION

Detecting attacks early in the field of cyber-security is crucial for mitigating potential damage to the system. Utilizing previous traffic classification results, automatic countermeasures can be promptly deployed. In our previous work [1], we introduced an end-to-end signature-based Intrusion Detection System (IDS) capable of accurately identifying and classifying network attacks at the earliest stages. By identifying and classifying a network attack in its early stages allows one not only to react timely but also to deploy countermeasures specific to the class of attack detected. Leveraging a Deep Neural Network (DNN) [2], we extracted pertinent features from raw network traffic to enable early attack classification. To assess the IDS's ability to detect attacks before their completion, we introduced a novel metric termed "earliness" to measure the fraction of the attack information used by the network for classifying an attack as a specific type. A tool, named EARLY was implemented to support our approach and discussed in [3]. There, the approach was implemented using two different neural network models, a CNN and an RNN, and both model types were evaluated on the CICIDS2017 dataset from the web application domain and, respectively, on the MQTT-IDS-2020 dataset from the IoT domain.

In additional research [4], we expanded upon our previous methodology by integrating an attention mechanism to enhance not only the classification performance and early detection but also the explainability of the approach. This

mechanism empowers the DNN to concentrate on more relevant packets within the network traffic data, thereby improving both classification accuracy and the timeliness of detection. We assessed the effectiveness of our approach by evaluating its performance against the CICIDS2017 dataset [5] within the web application domain.

In contrast to our previous work on the early classification of network attacks in which we used a Convolution Neural Network (CNN), in this work, we employ a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) with an attention mechanism, and we discuss and compare the results with the previous work. In addition to our previous work, the new model not only classifies a given flow but also ranks the packets in the flow with respect to their importance for the prediction. This ranking can be used for further investigation of the detected network attacks and for deploying more precise countermeasures. We empirically evaluate our approach to the CICIDS2017 dataset. Compared to current state-of-the-art approaches, our approach prioritizes the extraction of relevant features from raw network traffic for the early detection of attacks by leveraging the partial information available in the flows.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section II describes our approach. In Section III, we empirically evaluate our approach. Section IV presents an overview of the related work. Finally, Section V draws conclusions and discusses future work.

II. APPROACH

Our intrusion detection methodology operates on the granularity of network packets, examining network flows. Adopting the definition from [6], a *network flow* comprises bidirectional packet exchanges between two endpoints, like a web server and a client, occurring within a specific time frame and sharing common properties such as source and destination IP addresses, port numbers, and protocol type. In our investigation, we characterize a network flow as a sequence of T ordered packets, where T signifies the duration of a complete flow. We denote such a flow as:

$$\mathbf{f} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_T\}, \forall p_i \in \mathbb{R}^D \wedge 1 \leq i \leq T \quad (1)$$

where D is the size (or length) of a packet.

Our approach, facilitated by the EARLY tool [7], comprises four primary components (refer to Figure 1):

- A *flow processing module*, responsible for extracting flows from network traffic based on specified flow parameters. It then furnishes these flows to other modules, whether for training purposes or ongoing monitoring.
- A *training module*, utilized to train neural network models employing diverse datasets tailored to various application domains (e.g., web, IoT, etc.).
- A *repository of attack models* housing trained models designed for different attack types across various application domains.
- A *monitoring module* oversees network traffic utilizing a trained model from the repository. Upon detecting attacks, this module initiates alerts based on predefined triggers to implement automatic countermeasures.

The focus of this paper is the training module, while we defer further details about the other modules to the previous publication [1]. The training module uses a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) [8] model to extract a good internal representation of network flows. Each node in an RNN model has a memory unit (i.e., also known as the *hidden state*) that represents the previous state of the network. The current hidden state h_t is a function of the previous hidden state h_{t-1} and the current input (i.e., a packet in our case) p_t : $h_t = f(h_{t-1}, p_t)$, where t represents the current time step. Subsequently, the current hidden state h_t is used to compute the final output of the node, denoted as a *feature vector* $\mathbf{m}_t = \{y_t^{(1)}, \dots, y_t^{(B)}\}$, $y \in \mathbb{R}$. We use Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) [9] as shown in Figure 2. GRU is a variant of RNN, which can learn long-term sequential dependencies efficiently because it does not suffer from the vanishing gradient issue as opposed to other variants of RNN such as LSTM [10]. In addition, GRUs are reportedly slightly faster and easier to run, although less expressive than LSTMs [11]. The distinguishing features of a GRU cell are the *update gate* and the *reset gate*. The former keeps track of the most important information and

which information is passed to the next cell. The latter identifies less important (unnecessary) information to be discarded from the GRU.

Fig. 2. Generic GRU architecture

We use a GRU layer with B units to extract a set of relevant feature vectors from the network's raw traffic. We define the set of feature vectors: $m = \{\mathbf{m}_1, \dots, \mathbf{m}_T\}$, $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{R}^B$. In this study, we propose an extension to our existing approach by integrating an attention mechanism (AM). The AM is a well-established deep learning technique that enables models to selectively focus on pertinent elements within an input sequence, as opposed to treating all elements equally [12]. In our context, AM allows the model to dynamically assign weights to individual network packets within a flow, providing insights into which aspects of the network data the model deems most significant during analysis. Notably, the AM has seen significant success in natural language processing tasks like machine translation and text summarization, where models must concentrate on specific words within a sentence for accurate meaning comprehension.

We adopt the additive attention mechanism proposed by Bahdanau et al. [13] to compute a context vector $c \in \mathbb{R}^B$. This vector integrates the feature vectors (representing individual packets in a flow) while accounting for their relative importance in class prediction. The context vector is calculated as a weighted sum of the feature vectors, with the weights determined by the corresponding *attention scores* α_t :

$$c = \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t \mathbf{m}_t \quad (2)$$

The attention mechanism assigns a non-negative score α_t to each feature vector \mathbf{m}_t . This score can be interpreted as the probability that the feature vector of packet t holds the most relevant information for predicting the flow's class. The attention score α_t of each feature vector \mathbf{m}_t is calculated as:

$$\alpha_t = \frac{\exp(s_t)}{\sum_{t=1}^T \exp(s_t)} \quad (3)$$

$$s_t = att(\mathbf{m}_t) \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1. Overview of EARLY tool architecture.

where *att* is an attention sub-model. It is implemented as a fully-connected layer and is jointly trained with the rest of the model. A subsequent section will provide a concrete example with a graphical representation of the neural network architecture in Figure 3.

III. EVALUATION

We evaluate the performance of our approach by answering the following research questions:

- RQ1: How does the attention mechanism affect the classification performance of our approach in terms of classifying the complete flows (i.e., flows with all the packets)?
- RQ2: Does the attention mechanism make the approach more effective in identifying the class of a given flow in real-time by inspecting only the first few packets of the flow?
- RQ3: Can our approach identify the packets of a given flow that are more important for predictions?

A. Dataset

We assess the efficacy of our approach using the CICSIDS2017 dataset [5], which comprises normal traffic as well as seven types of attack flows, such as Heartbleed, Botnet, and Web attacks, each accompanied by the corresponding network packets.

Specifically, we utilize a subset of the dataset captured on Thursday, July 6, 2017, containing network flows associated with various web attacks, including SQL Injection, Cross-Site Scripting (XSS), and Brute Force. In SQL Injection, an attacker inserts a string of SQL commands into the database. XSS involves injecting a script into the web application code, while Brute Force entails attempting a series of passwords to discover the administrator’s password.

The breakdown of the number of flows and the average flow length (i.e., number of packets) per class in the Thursday dataset is presented in Table I.

We have noted that in 99% of the packets within our dataset, the header length is equal to or less than 40 bytes, while the payload length is equal to or less than 356 bytes. To accommodate packets with varying header and payload lengths, we either crop or pad them with zeros, ensuring that the header length reaches 50 bytes and the payload length extends to 400 bytes. Additionally, we normalize all packet bytes to a range between 0 and 1 by dividing them by 255. This normalization process is known to aid in the quicker convergence of machine learning algorithms [14].

TABLE I
LABELED FLOW DATASET

Class	Number of Flows	Average Flow length
Normal	27 129	124.39
Brute Force	1 507	18.43
XSS	652	11.48
SQL Injection	21	5.71

The dataset was divided into two parts, adhering to a 70:30 split for the training and testing sets, as detailed in Table II. It is evident from the data that there is a significant imbalance among the flow classes; for instance, the normal class encompasses approximately 1291.86 times more flows than the SQL Injection class. To partition the original dataset, we employed stratified sampling as discussed in [15]. This method differs from random sampling by ensuring that each class is represented in the splits at the same proportion as found in the full dataset.

TABLE II
TRAINING AND TEST DATASETS

Class	Training	Test
Normal	18 990	8 139
Brute Force	1 055	452
XSS	456	196
SQL Injection	15	6

B. Model Architecture

Our neural network model (shown in Figure 3) has a GRU layer with 32 units, *Tanh* activation, and bias. The attention model *Attention* has a fully connected layer of size 32. This sub-model takes the set of feature vectors as input from the GRU layer and returns the *context vector* of size 32 and the *attention score vector*. The context vector is then provided as input to a *Dense* layer with *Softmax* activation to obtain a probability distribution for each class. Based on the probability distribution and the classification threshold, we make the final predictions. The attention score vector ranks the packets in the flow with respect to their importance for prediction. This ranking can be used for further investigation of the detected network attacks. The total number of trainable parameters of the model is 47,493.

For evaluation purposes, we denote the model from our previous work [4] as *eCNN* and the model in Figure 3 as *eRNN*.

C. Training

The *eCNN* and *eRNN* models are trained and evaluated against the independent test set that is extracted from the dataset. During the training phase, we adjust the importance of each sample or flow by assigning weights based on their class, calculated as the inverse of the class’s frequency in the training dataset. This approach aims to enhance the classifier’s ability to accurately identify instances from less prevalent classes. The utilization of cost-sensitive learning, as opposed to methods based on altering sample distribution, has shown superior performance in addressing imbalances across various domains, as reported in [16].

To optimize hyper-parameters and select the best model, we employ 10-fold cross-validation on the training data. To ensure statistical robustness, this evaluation process is conducted 20 times with a preliminary random shuffle of the dataset to eliminate any sequence bias before dividing it into training and testing sets. We have fixed the number of training epochs at 50.

Fig. 3. Model architecture

D. Evaluation Metrics

Most existing intrusion detection tools employing machine learning typically rely on traditional metrics like accuracy and F1-score to gauge their performance. However, these metrics are tailored for evaluating classifiers on balanced datasets and tend to perform poorly when faced with substantial class distribution imbalances within the dataset [17]. Consequently, we opt to evaluate our tool using the following metrics, all with values between 0 and 1:

- Precision: Measures the proportion of instances identified as positive that were correctly classified.
- Recall (also known as detection rate): Quantifies the percentage of actual positive instances that were correctly classified.
- False positive rate (FPR) (also known as false alarm rate): Estimates the ratio of negative observations wrongly predicted as positive to the total number of negative observations.
- Balanced Accuracy (BA) represents the arithmetic mean of recall obtained on each class.
- Bookmaker Informedness (BM): Defined as the probability that the classifier will make a correct decision as opposed to random guessing.
- Prediction time: Indicates the average time required by the tool to detect a security attack.

In addition, we use a metric called *earliness* and defined in [1], with values between 0 and 1, which assesses the minimum number of packets t necessary for accurately predicting the class of a particular flow out of the total number of packets of that flow T . Given that this metric specifically assesses the timeliness of predictions rather than their accuracy, it is solely applied to flows that are correctly classified. Earliness can be calculated with the following formula:

$$Earliness = \begin{cases} \frac{T-t}{T-1} & \text{if } T > 1 \\ 1 & \text{if } T = 1 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Alongside the previously mentioned metrics, we present the macro and weighted average values for precision, recall, and FPR metrics. The macro average value, representing the arithmetic mean, offers an impartial evaluation of the classification performance of a model across all classes, irrespective of their

prevalence in the dataset. Conversely, the weighted average value addresses the dataset's imbalance by assigning greater importance to the metrics of classes with higher instance counts.

E. RQ1: Classification Performance

The objective of this research question is to investigate how the classification performance of our approach is affected by the attention mechanism.

Table III presents a comparison of the classification effectiveness of our methodology, utilizing two network models, on the test dataset. The highest performance for each metric across the models is highlighted in bold within the table. Notably, the *eRNN* model has consistently outperformed the *eCNN* model in terms of classification performance. However, in the context of XSS attacks, our model exhibits a marginally lower precision, accompanied by a slightly higher rate of false positives. Further, the *eRNN* model has achieved higher balanced accuracy (i.e., 0.924) than the *eCNN* model (i.e., 0.853).

F. RQ2: Earliness Performance

The focus of this research question is to explore how early our method can accurately identify threats when incorporating an attention mechanism. We believe that an effective real-time IDS must meet two criteria. Firstly, it should process data (i.e., network packets) at the pace they are generated under typical conditions. Secondly, the minimum number of packets needed to reliably determine the class of a network flow (MNP) ought to be fewer than the total packet count in that flow.

To investigate this, we conducted a replay experiment simulating the network traffic captured in our dataset on the two models *eCNN* and *eRNN*, to mimic a real-time setting. This experiment was performed using separate computers for our method and the traffic simulation. Each system was equipped with an Intel Core i9-10900X CPU, 64 GB RAM, and an RTX 3090 graphics card, and ran on Ubuntu 22.04 OS, linked through a 1Gb Ethernet in a controlled environment to minimize network delay.

During the experiment, which lasted 29,146 seconds, a total of 9,322,025 packets were retransmitted. We adjusted the packet filtering tool to pass only packets with destination or source port 80, focusing on web attack detection. Nonetheless,

TABLE III
CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE COMPARED BETWEEN THE PROPOSED MODEL AND THE ECNN MODEL FROM IN OUR PREVIOUS WORK

Class	Precision			Recall			FPR			BM		
	eRNN	eCNN	Diff.	eRNN	eCNN	Diff.	eRNN	eCNN	Diff.	eRNN	eCNN	Diff.
Normal	1.000	0.997	0.3%	0.994	0.964	3.0%	0.001	0.033	-3200.0%	0.994	0.931	6.3%
Brute force	0.931	0.641	31.1%	0.886	0.881	0.6%	0.003	0.028	-833.3%	0.883	0.853	3.4%
XSS	0.806	0.820	-1.7%	0.968	0.886	8.5%	0.008	0.005	37.5%	0.961	0.881	8.3%
SQL Injection	0.343	0.094	72.6%	0.845	0.692	18.1%	0.002	0.008	-300.0%	0.844	0.692	18.0%
Macro average	0.770	0.638	17.1%	0.924	0.856	7.4%	0.003	0.019	-533.3%	0.920	0.837	9.0%
Weighted average	0.992	0.974	1.8%	0.988	0.958	3.0%	0.001	0.032	-3100.0%	0.987	0.925	6.3%

our method supports the selection of various ports or port combinations for tailored detection needs.

In the replay session, we tracked the inter-arrival times of packets, the time our method took to predict, and the minimum number of packets required (MNP) for accurate flow class prediction. The average inter-arrival time was 15.96 milliseconds. On average, predictions using the *eRNN* model were made in 0.43 milliseconds per packet, which is slower by 0.36 milliseconds compared to the *eCNN* model. However, the prediction time per packet remains below the average packet inter-arrival time, indicating our method can analyze network packets quicker than their arrival rate, fulfilling the first criterion for an effective real-time IDS. Furthermore, we observed that the improvement concerning the earliness metric was either identical or exhibited a negligible difference when compared to *eCNN*. As a result, we have chosen not to present the detailed comparison in Table IV to avoid redundancy and maintain clarity.

TABLE IV
EARLINESS METRIC AND THE AVERAGE MINIMUM NUMBER OF PACKETS REQUIRED (MNP) TO PREDICT THE FLOW CLASS

Class	Avg. flow length	Earliness	MNP
Normal	124.39	0.992	1.99
Brute force	18.43	0.964	1.63
XSS	11.48	0.923	1.81
SQL Injection	5.71	0.796	1.96

G. RQ3: Explainability

Figure 4 illustrates the averaged/aggregated normalized attention scores assigned to the first ten packets to every flow in the test dataset, as derived from our model. The x-axis of the chart represents the packet position within a given flow, while the y-axis indicates the corresponding attention scores. By examining the attention score distribution across different flow types, we can gain valuable insights into the unique characteristics and communication patterns within each traffic category. High attention scores on specific packets could indicate their importance in distinguishing flow types, while packets with low attention scores might suggest their general prevalence across categories.

As one can notice, high attention scores concentrated on initial packets for each flow category indicate the importance of establishing connections and requesting resources. This aligns with the values of the earliness metric, which shows

that on average we needed the first 2-3 packets per flow to classify it. However, we consistently observed significantly higher attention scores attributed to the fourth packet in the flow sequences related to the SQL Injection attack, suggesting a focus on the payload content. Upon closer inspection of the fourth packet (outlined in Listing 1), we discovered that it consistently carried the malicious SQL query (line 1), attempting to exploit a specific database vulnerability. This finding corroborates the attention score patterns and highlights the importance of explainability which allows us to delve deeper into individual packets to uncover hidden patterns and potential attack vectors.

Listing 1. Packet payload related to the SQL Injection attack

```

1 GET /dv/vulnerabilities/sqli/?id=1%27+and+1%3D1+union+
  select+null%2C+table_name+from+information_schema.
  tables%23&Submit=Submit HTTP/1.1
2 User-Agent: Mozilla/5.0 (X11; Linux x86_64; rv:45.0)
  Gecko/20100101 Firefox/45.0
3 Accept: text/html,application/xhtml+xml,application/xml;
  q=0.9, */*;q=0.8
4 Referer: http://205.174.165.68/dv/vulnerabilities/sqli/?
  id=1%27+and+1%3D1+union+select+database%28%29%2C+
  user%28%29%23&Submit=Submit
5 Connection: keep-alive

```

This malicious code corresponds to the following SQL query

Listing 2. Query of the SQL Injection attack

```

1 id=1' and 1=1
2 UNION SELECT null, table_name
3 FROM information_schema.tables

```

IV. RELATED WORK

Several studies that have incorporated attention mechanisms have reported enhancements in learning from imbalanced datasets and in detection accuracy. For example, research documented in [18] demonstrates the use of an LSTM model combined with an attention mechanism for a dynamic network anomaly detection system, achieving higher classification accuracy than other machine learning models and noting advantages in dealing with imbalanced datasets. Another study [19] introduces a method utilizing a hierarchical attention-based GRU model to analyze network flows, emphasizing statistical features derived from all packets within a flow. This contrasts with our method, which prioritizes the extraction of relevant features from raw network traffic for the early detection of attacks, leveraging the partial information available in the flows.

Fig. 4. Packets ranking for different attack classes

Moreover, the study in [19] combines a multi-head attention network and a gated convolution network, incorporating a Structure-Level Segmentation (SLS) technique for data structuring, aimed at identifying malicious web application requests. This method shows improved performance over alternatives, though it remains uncertain whether the attention mechanism or the SLS method primarily drives this enhancement.

Laghrissi et al. [20], propose an IDS that employs an LSTM network and attention mechanism to highlight significant network traffic features. Their approach, similar to [18], focuses on statistical features from complete flows, unlike ours, which identifies crucial features from raw traffic for prompt attack detection. Furthermore, they suggest using a conventional feed-forward neural network for processing fixed-size vectors, arguing that LSTM and attention mechanisms are best suited for lengthy sequential data. In our case, we utilize a 1D-CNN to handle variable-length network flows and an attention mechanism to selectively focus on the most pertinent packets within a flow.

These pieces of research support our observations and underscore the significance of further exploring attention mechanisms in this field.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the initial application of an attention-based RNN model for early detection of network attacks. By dynamically focusing on the most relevant network packets within the flow, the attention mechanism demonstrably improved the classification performance of the model compared to traditional RNN approaches. Our empirical evaluation on the CICIDS2017 dataset yielded encouraging results. Compared to our previous work, the attention-based RNN achieved superior classification performance, demonstrating the effectiveness of focusing on relevant network traffic aspects. Moreover, the attention mechanism fosters interpretability, providing valuable insights into the model's rationale behind each prediction. This feature allows network administrators to understand the decision-making process and potentially gain valuable insights about the nature of potential attacks. Future work will involve extensive testing on diverse datasets, optimizing the model architecture, and exploring the integration of interpretability tools for a deeper understanding of the learned attention patterns.

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